

Driver state monitoring employing the Human Performance Envelope model

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Abstract - The field of driving safety is significantly influenced by human factors, particularly within the automated driving context. This study explores the application of the Human Performance Envelope (HPE) model to Driver Monitoring Systems (DMS), with the aim of mapping and interpreting driver parameters. The study is grounded in the utilisation of an instrumented steering wheel, capable of detecting forces, moments and grip applied by the driver during a realistic driving simulation developed at the DriSMi laboratory of the Politecnico di Milano. Seven participants were presented with scenarios encompassing the transition from automated to manual driving, experiencing critical situations such as a roadwork site and emergency braking. Preliminary results on instrumented steering wheel analysis demonstrate the potential of the measured parameters to construct HPE maps, which may contribute to the identification of performance decrements and the enhancement of safety in self-driving vehicles. This approach offers novel perspectives to integrate human factors into DMS.

Keywords: Human Performance Envelope, DMS, Driving Simulator, Instrumented Steering Wheel.

Introduction

Human behaviour is one of the most challenging factors in driving safety (Iversen and Rundmo, 2004). Consequently, it is becoming increasingly important to address human factors related to Automated Driving Systems (ADS) (Heikoop, et al., 2019). In this regard, the Human Performance Envelope (HPE) represents a relatively new paradigm in Human Factors. Instead of concentrating on isolated elements, it encompasses nine factors commonly associated with accidents. Figure 1 shows all factors involved in the HPE definition and the resulting spider web. This approach maps how these factors, individually or in combination, contribute to performance decrements that may compromise safety. This concept was originally proposed in the Air Traffic Management (ATM) domain (Edwards, 2013; Edwards, et al., 2016). Firstly, the European project "Future Sky Safety: Human Performance Envelope" extended HPE to Human Operators in road vehicles' cockpits. This study aims to create the basis to extend the application of the HPE model to ground transportation, specifically focusing on its integration into driver-vehicle interactions. To achieve this objective, a series of trials was conducted using a dynamic driving simulator on a sample of 7 users. The objective of conducting a comprehensive evaluation was to achieve the most precise possible assessment. The following instrumentation was utilised to accomplish this objective, comprising an eye tracker device, an Electrocardio-

gram (ECG), an Electroencephalogram (EEG), and an Instrumented Steering Wheel (ISW). This paper presents the results of the ISW, which were obtained as a preliminary attempt to quantify HPE factors. The choice of this instrument is dictated by two main reasons. Firstly, it is one of the on-board instruments most applicable to the driving context, and secondly, there is solid previous experience in the literature confirming its validity (Comolli, Gobbi, and Mastinu, 2020).

Figure 1: Human Performance Envelope Factors

Figure 2: Experiment design. The vehicle automation level, the approximate time interval and the traffic condition are defined.

Research question

By analysing steering wheel parameters, this research investigates how the transition between manual and automated driving, as well as some critical and challenging driving events, affect HPE parameters. The aim is to provide a basis for determining how these parameters can be used in the development of HPE maps, providing insights into human behaviour in complex and dynamic traffic environments.

Methodology

A preliminary study is proposed to analyse the HPE model in a driving context. The experiment has been developed at the DriSMi Laboratory of Politecnico di Milano, hosting a dynamic driving simulator. As this test is exploratory, it was imperative to have data of the highest possible quality for all sensors. To this end, the test population comprised seven students with short hair. A four-lane highway with ongoing roadworks represents the simulation environment. At the beginning of the simulation (i.e., S_1), the vehicle drives with a Level 4 automation along the right lane with heavy traffic, within its Operational Design Domain (ODD). Due to roadworks, the vehicle exits its ODD and cannot continue the driving task (i.e., S_2). A Take-Over Request (TOR) is issued to the driver, who must perform a lane change moving to the left (i.e., S_3). Finally, the vehicle falls into a Level 0 automation, with the driver solely in charge of vehicle control. The driver needs to exit the roadworks zone (i.e., S_4) and continue driving in the last simulation section (i.e., S_5 with sparse traffic). At the end of this section, a vehicle ahead of the driver makes an emergency braking, forcing the driver to make a sudden manoeuvre. Automation levels are designed according to the SAE definition (Taxonomy, 2018). Figure 2 shows the complete simulation architecture.

Figure 3: Instrumented Steering Wheel (Akutain, et al., 2024)

Sensor	Fs	Measure	UoM
Dynamic Driving Simulator	500 Hz	Centre of Mass position	<i>m</i>
		Vehicle pitch, roll, and yaw	<i>rad</i>
		Vehicle longitudinal speed	<i>m/s</i>
		Vehicle lateral speed	<i>m/s</i>
		Vehicle longitudinal acceleration	<i>m/s²</i>
		Vehicle lateral acceleration	<i>m/s²</i>
		Brake pedal position	%
		Accelerator pedal position	%
ECG	500 Hz	Heart Rate (HR)	<i>bpm</i>
		Heart Rate Variability (HRV) Mean NN	<i>ms</i>
		HRV RMSSD	<i>ms</i>
		HRV ln(RMSSD)	<i>ms</i>
		HRV LF	<i>ms²</i>
		HRV HF	<i>ms²</i>
		HRV LF/HF	-
ISW	500 Hz	Driver grip force	<i>N</i>
EEG	1000 Hz	$\theta_{front}/\alpha_{par}$	-
		$\theta_{front}/\beta_{front}$	-
		α_{rel}	-
		θ_{rel}	-
		β_{rel}	-
Eye Tracker	25 Hz	Eyes Off Road Time (EORT)	%
		Saccades rate	<i>Hz</i>
		Saccades amplitude	<i>deg</i>
		Fixation time	<i>s</i>

Table 1: Testbed sensors and measures retrieved. Sampling frequency (i.e., F_s) and Unit of Measure (UoM) are listed.

Figure 4: Total compensated grip force for each subject during the simulation. Times related to take over request, control taken, and braking event are also highlighted. The difference between the take over request time and the control taken time represents the Take Over Time (TOT).

Testbed

The main component of the experiment is the dynamic driving simulator. It is a new-generation, medium-sized simulator composed of two stages. The first is represented by a cable-driven platform, featuring a 4x4 m longitudinal-lateral displacement. The second stage is a hexapod providing a six-degree-of-freedom motion up to 30 Hz. Finally, the visual and auditory equipment comprises a 270° screen and a five-speaker system. This powerful simulator guarantees high immersiveness and realism during tests (Cheli, et al., 2022). The subsequent table (Table 1) provides a comprehensive overview of the sensors utilised during the test execution in the simulated environment. In addition to the sensors, the table provides the sampling frequency, the type of measurement that can be obtained from the individual sensor, and its unit of measurement.

ISW data analysis

This paper presents the results of the Instrumented Steering Wheel (ISW) data. Specifically, the ISW is composed of six spokes and two handles. The two central spokes are equipped with two six-axis load cells, which track forces and moments components on each hand. Moreover, each handle carries three mono-axial load cells to analyse driver grip. ISW is used to retrieve drivers' grip during the simulation. The data recorded are pre-processed, attenuating high-frequency noise (i.e., zero-phase low-pass filter, cutoff frequency=2Hz). Afterwards, the grip force on each handle is calculated by the following equation.

$$F_{\text{grip}} = \min \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^3 F_i - \min \{ F_x, 0 \}, 0 \right\} \quad (1)$$

F_x represents the force applied in the axial direction measured by the spoke's six-axis load cell, while F_i is the force measured by each of the three mono-axial load cells mounted on the handles. Before calculating the grip force, each force and moment component is compensated considering the steering wheel inertial, tangential and centripetal acceleration components, and the vehicle's rotational and linear inertial components. The total grip force is obtained by summing up the grip forces on the two handles, F_{gripL} and F_{gripR} respectively. The grip force is always negative and higher for more negative values, since a compression force is applied by the driver to the ISW. Figure 4 shows the resulting total grip force for each subject during the simulation, highlighting three key events.

1. Take Over Request (TOR). Time at which the driver received the TOR from the vehicle.
2. Control taken. The time instant when the driver regains control of the vehicle.
3. Braking event. Time at which the vehicle preceding the driver starts a sudden braking manoeuvre.

The time interval between the TOR and the control taken represents the Take Over Time (TOT) for each subject.

Three processing windows, each lasting 8 seconds, are extracted from the total grip force time history. They are related to the three key events.

1. First window. Starting from the control taken time instant. It is used to study the driver's behaviour right after they regain vehicle control.

2. Second window. During section 4, as far as possible to section 3. It shows how the driver behaves during a normal driving phase. It is considered far from section 3 to maximise the habituation effect of the individual to the driving context and to reduce the effect of the take over in section 3.
3. Third window. It begins as soon as the driver brakes during the braking event. It is used to understand how the driver responds to a sudden input coming from the driving context.

From the processing windows, the total grip mean is extracted and compared over the three events.

Figure 5: Mean grip for each subject during the three processing windows.

Looking at Figure 5 it is possible to investigate the mean grip trend over the three processing windows. Specifically, an ascending trend is highlighted starting from the TOR, through the normal driving event, and culminating in the braking event.

Conclusions

This preliminary study investigated the applicability of the Human Performance Envelope (HPE) model to Driver Monitoring Systems (DMS) in the context of partially automated driving. The results, based on grip force data obtained through an Instrumented Steering Wheel (ISW), show a significant correlation between the complexity of driving scenarios and driver grip force: specifically, an increasing trend in mean grip was observed from the takeover event to normal driving and, finally, during the emergency braking phase. This trend suggests that grip force can be used as a reliable indicator of driver vigilance and stress, contributing to the real-time estimation of the driver's state within the HPE framework.

These findings offer a promising basis for the integration of HPE-based metrics into next-generation DMS, potentially enabling systems to anticipate performance degradations and improve both driving safety and comfort, by supporting the adaptation of vehicle dynamics in real time based on the driver's physiological state.

The ISW has proven to be a non-intrusive and reliable source of behavioural data, suitable for integration into real vehicle applications. Effectively using this information could significantly enhance driver assistance technologies.

Future analyses will include data from additional physiological and behavioural sensors to draw a more comprehensive Human Performance Envelope, considering all the interrelations between the different human state parameters.

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